

CHARACTERISTICS OF COOPERATION IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKMENISTAN

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Abstract: The Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have lived with common goals as close friends, friendly neighbors, and strategic partners since time immemorial. Therefore, the roots of the relations between the two countries go back to a long history and are built on the basis of mutual respect and trust. Uzbek and Turkmen peoples have been drinking water from the same river for a long time and lived peacefully and harmoniously. Our peoples are united by a common history, common culture and values, similar language and customs. This closeness is the basis of strong cooperation between our countries.

Keywords: Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, neighbour, region, cooperation, government, association

Introduction :Cooperation in the field of higher education is an important area of bilateral or multilateral relations, and its development fully meets the aspirations of the peoples of the region. "A new professional education system will be launched. the level of coverage of school graduates with higher education should be increased to at least 25% in 2020 and 50-60% in the future. State grants for admission of students to higher educational institutions will be doubled, special grants will be allocated for girls. the educational process in higher education will be transferred to the credit-module system, higher educational institutions will be transferred to self-financing, at least 5 higher educational institutions will be transformed." Cooperation in the field of higher education in the Central Asian region in the post-Soviet period was heterogeneous (from the Greek, diversity is the presence of unequal parts in the structure of something). Reforms in the system of education and science in each of the Central Asian countries have their own special features. The norms defined in our constitution, the Law "On Education", the National Personnel Training Program and the normative documents adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Cabinet of Ministers serve as a solid legal foundation in this regard. In the areas of higher educationteaching is conducted in Tajik, Kazakh, Turkmen and Kyrgyz languages.

Contracts and Results

Cooperation in the field of higher education is an important area of bilateral or multilateral relations, and its development fully meets the aspirations of the peoples of the region. "A new professional education system will be launched. the level of coverage of school graduates with higher education should be increased to at least 25% in 2020 and 50-60% in the future. State grants for admission of students to higher educational institutions will be doubled, special grants will be allocated for girls. the educational process in higher education will be transferred to the credit-module system, higher educational institutions will be transferred to self-financing, at least 5 higher educational institutions will be transformed." [1].

Cooperation in the field of higher education in the Central Asian region in the post-Soviet period was heterogeneous (from the Greek, diversity is the presence of unequal parts in the structure of something). Reforms in the system of education and science in each of the Central

Asian countries have their own special features. In the early 90s of the last century, due to the transition of the regional countries to market relations, the problem of supplying textbooks and educational literature to Uzbek diasporas in neighboring republics and to students studying in sister languages in Uzbekistan arose. In the 2000-2001 academic year in Uzbekistan, 175,606 students were educated in Turkmen, Tajik and Kyrgyz languages, and they were fully provided with textbooks and study guides. Article 33 of the Law "On Education" entitled "International cooperation" states that "Educational institutions participate in international cooperation on educational issues, establish direct relations with relevant educational institutions of foreign countries, joint training with them in accordance with the procedure established by law based on the rule that states "have the right to establish"[2], from the first years of independence, Uzbekistan established relations and cooperation in the field of education with all countries, especially the Central Asian republics. cooperation in the field of education is still considered one of the promising directions of mutual cooperation between the countries of Central Asia, and cooperation in this field occupies a special place in the development of regional relations. International cooperation is one of the most rapidly developing areas of higher education in Uzbekistan. There are many opportunities to study abroad thanks to intergovernmental agreements.

Like other universities, UzMU, TDIU, TDTU, and UzDJTU have signed bilateral beneficial agreements with foreign universities on their own initiative, and extensive work is underway in the field of exchange of teachers, graduate students, interns, scientific research, educational and methodological developments, and textbooks was placed [3]. From the first years of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan signed intergovernmental agreements with neighboring countries in the field of education. The cooperation agreement in the field of education (Chorjuy 16.01.1996 (Appendix 10)) was signed between the governments of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan [4], which were automatically extended every five years from the date of signing these documents became the legal basis for the establishment and development of bilateral cooperation in the field of education International cooperation was carried out in the following directions: establishment of joint higher education institutions, involvement of foreign teachers and scientists in the teaching process in republican higher education institutions, promotion of academic mobility and joint research activities; higher education, innovative organization of international conferences on current issues in the field of technology, resource and energy saving, attraction of foreign investments. An Advisory Council of the heads of state organizations managing the field of science and technology of Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan was established. In 1992, the agreement between the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Ministry of Culture and Tourism of Turkmenistan for the period of 1992-1995 has an important place in cooperation between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan in the field of education, science and personnel training and based on it, cooperation between countries in the field of education was developing. On the basis of normative legal documents on cooperation between the two countries, a number of higher education institutions in Uzbekistan established cooperation relations with higher education institutions and scientific centers of the Republic of Turkmenistan. In 1993, Karshi State University, Kashkadarya "Mihit" and "Zarin Nur" scientific production centers of the university in cooperation with the "Karshi Tolas" association of the agro-industrial association of the region, "Cybernetics" scientific-

production association of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, and the Academy of Sciences of Turkmenistan. Scientific research on analyzing the structure of irrigated lands in Kashkadarya region and studying parameters of water movement speed and hydrodynamic properties in pipes and canals of various configurations with the scientists of "Kuyosh" Scientific and Production Center research was conducted. In 1993, the head of the scientific laboratory of this scientific-industrial association, senior researcher, doctors of technical sciences K. Dattended, in addition, more than 10 scientific articles were published in cooperation with this association.

In 1996, the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Turkmenistan signed another document - "Agreement on cooperation in the field of culture between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan", in which cooperation in the field of science and education was noted. [5] In 1997-1998, the Scientific and Research Institute of Solar Energy Utilization of the CISF of Turkmenistan established scientific and research cooperation with the Karakalpak State University

In August 1998, 13 out of 40 places reserved for foreign citizens at the State Pedagogical University of Turkmenistan, young people from Uzbekistan entered. In 1999, 19 students from Turkmenistan studied at 5 HEIs of Uzbekistan. [6]

The program "Economic cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Republic of Turkmenistan for the period of 2013-2017" signed between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan in October 2012 establishes mutual relations of higher education institutions between these countries establishment and development, academic exchange with the participation of professors and teachers in the field of education, became a legal basis for carrying out scientific and research work in cooperation. [7] By 2014, 59 students from Turkmenistan enrolled in higher education institutions of Kashkadarya region alone. including 45 students at Karshi State University, 1 student at Karshi Institute of Engineering and Economics, 13 students at TATU Karshi branch. In 2018, there were 720 students from the Republic of Turkmenistan in higher education institutions of Uzbekistan. On May 20, 2017, in the city of Turkmanbashi, Turkmenistan, an agreement between Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami and Turkmenistan State Pedagogical Institute named after Seyitnazar Seydi within the framework of cooperation in the field of higher education signed. Based on this agreement, it was agreed to cooperate between the universities in academic exchange of professors - teachers and students, as well as scientific, educational - methodical direction

On March 31, 2010, a scientific conference was held at the Institute of Language and Literature of the UzR FA together with the Embassy of Turkmenistan in Uzbekistan on the occasion of the 200th anniversary of the famous Turkmen poet Mullanafas. leading specialists participated in many international conferences, symposiums and seminars held in Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. [8]

On March 6, 2017, an agreement "On Economic Cooperation for 2018-2020" was signed between the Republic of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan in Ashgabat. [9] This agreement includes not only cooperation between the two countries in the fields of trade and economy, transport communications, environmental protection and rational use of nature, health care and tourism development, but also in the field of education and science establishment of organic relations was envisaged. in particular, the development of relations between higher educational institutions of the two countries, international higher educational institutions of

countries such as Russia, Great Britain, Italy, and institutes and universities of Uzbekistan operating in Tashkent. Issues such as attracting Turkmen students, establishing exchange of professors and academic staff, organization of international conferences and participation in them were put forward.

On December 14-15, 1993, according to the proposal of the scientists of the Kyrgyz Republic, natural scientists of Andijan State University at the scientific conference held at Osh State University on priority environmental problems presented their Fergana Valley participated with the results of scientific research on ecology (conference materials were published). [10]

Conclusion

Based on the above, it is worth noting that, although the Central Asian countries gained their independence more than a quarter of a century ago, their mutual cooperation in training and exchange of personnel is developing very slowly. is one of the fields. In this way, there is a lack of continuous communication and cooperation programs, and those that exist are not implemented significantly. Therefore, it is appropriate for relevant organizations to conduct separate research studies and analytical reports in this regard.

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